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Smart tags for traceability in cereal and dairy value chains

Summary

Smart tags provide a cost-effective and scalable solution for digital traceability in food supply chains. These tags link physical products to a digital identity, enabling access to detailed product and process information, enhancing transparency, and supporting quality and anti-counterfeiting measures. Smart tags use printed 2D barcodes to connect physical items with digital records, allowing for traceability and information exchange accessible via smartphones and standard vision systems. They become smart when linked to databases or blockchains for updated and validated product data. Functional inks and indicators, such as oxygen-sensitive colour-changing inks, can be integrated with 2D barcodes to monitor environmental or product conditions, signalling package opening or spoilage risks. Watson project presented smart tags as access keys to a broader platform that includes product digital identities, event histories, immutable data records, interoperability standards, and AI-supported tools for authenticity and early warnings.

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Introduction to smart tags

In the 2020s, food supply chains have been forced into a very public “stress test”: climate volatility, geopolitical shocks, recurring food fraud incidents, and rising consumer expectations for transparency have all collided with the reality that food is perishable, globally traded, and operationally challenging. In this environment, printable Smart Tags, most implemented as two-dimensional (2D) barcodes such as QR Codes and Data Matrix, have become one of the most pragmatic building blocks for digital traceability and information exchange. Unlike “smart labels” that rely on embedded electronics, printed 2D codes are cheap, scalable, production-line friendly, and readable with standard machine vision systems and consumer smartphones. They can even contain information that can be read by humans. Smart Tags core value is simple: they create a robust bridge between a physical item (a package, batch, pallet, or case) and its digital identity, enabling access to structured products and process information far beyond what can fit on a conventional label. Figure 1 illustrates an integration of a Smart Tag on a beer bottle.

Figure 1. Watson 2D barcode, a Datamatrix, in a beer bottle

A printed 2D barcode is not “smart” by itself. It becomes a Smart Tag when it is treated as a persistent identifier tied to digital records that can be updated, queried, and validated across the supply chain. In practice, this means linking the code to databases, block-chains and traceability platforms that store origin data, processing events, quality certificates, cold-chain history, and recall-related metadata. Research in food packaging and supply chain integrity highlights that QR-enabled packaging is increasingly used as a high-capacity, rapid-access channel for information transmission, supporting traceability, quality communication, and anti-counterfeiting measures, especially when paired with well-governed backend systems (Li et al., 2024). The 2020s have also normalized scanning behavior through everyday smartphone use, lowering the behavioral barrier for consumers and frontline operators to interact with digital product information at the point of purchase, in logistics, and even in food service contexts. (Isohanni, 2022)

Furthermore, intelligence withing Smart Tags can be increased by integration monitoring functionalities through the use of functional inks as well as printed indicators and sensors (Hakola et al, 2019). These monitoring functionalities react to changes in product, package, or environmental conditions with a visual colour change detectable by a mobile application when the Smart Tag is scanned. Physcially Unclonable Functions (PUFs) that use package or label fiber structures, for example, as unique identifiers, offer additional functionality to increase security features of Smart Tags.

Smart tag technologies in Watson

This section introduces three building blocks of the Watson smart-tag approach: visual sensors, the smart-tag platform concept, and security features based on PUFs. First, it describes printed functional inks and indicators, with a concrete example of an oxygen indicator that changes from yellow to blue and can be integrated with a 2D barcode to reveal package opening or oxygen exposure. Next, it explains how smart tags act as an access key to a wider platform that links each product to a “passport-like” digital identity and an event history across the supply chain. Finally, it outlines how Physically Unclonable Functions add a unique, hard-to-copy physical fingerprint to support reliable authentication and anti-fraud use cases.

Visual sensors

Smart tags are used as data carriers in intelligent packaging applications, and they typically consist of printed functional layers, indicators and/or sensors, and data carrier parts. Indicators are qualitative or semi-quantitative visual or optical sensors. They can be functional inks that change their color when the conditions change, such as temperature or humidity exceeding a threshold temperature. Indicators can also be more complex systems with activation and encapsulation and detect even presence of oxygen or volatile compounds. In the context of WATSON project, functional inks and indicators have been evaluated for their feasibility to monitor food products and environmental conditions.

Watson project focused on an oxygen indicator that was based on utilizing oxidation-reduction reaction. The indicator was printed in a normal atmosphere and afterwards activated through a reduction reaction using heat in oxygen-free environment. Figure 2 presents the principle of the color change and integration concept with a 2D barcode. Oxygen indicators are, therefore, capable of showing if an oxygen-free package has been opened, thus alerting potential for package tampering because of counterfeiting attempts. Furthermore, oxygen indicators can also indicate if there is a risk for spoilage of oxygen-sensitive food products.

Figure 2. (a) Color change of oxygen indicators developed in WATSON project from yellow to blue when exposed to oxygen. (b) Integration of oxygen indicator with a 2D barcode. Oxygen indicator is a yellow or blue bar at the bottom of the 2D barcode. Yellow background is used to make the yellow bar invisible to reading applications.

Smart tag platform

In the Watson project, smart tags are presented not as a standalone label upgrade, but as an access key to a broader platform that couples product identity, shared histories, interoperability standards, and anti-fraud intelligence. Using the Finnish cereal and dairy chains as an illustrative case (beer and cheese), Watson frames smart tags as an enabling layer for digital product identities and “passport-like” records that support rapid verification, accountability, and targeted response when integrity or safety is challenged. This text synthesizes what can be reliably extracted from the Watson cereal and dairy use case description and the project’s publication portfolio, emphasizing platform logic, data and governance requirements, and the role of complementary analytical and AI-based toolsets.

From the Finnish cereal and dairy use case description, the Watson platform model can be understood as five coupled components:

(1) Product-level digital identity (“passport” concept). Watson describes giving each product a traceable digital identity, explicitly compared to a “passport” that follows the item from farm to end-consumer. This identity is accessed by scanning a code on the product and is intended to consolidate provenance and process information into a single, accessible view (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

(2) Event-based data capture across the chain. In the cereal and dairy narrative, data is captured at multiple points: ingredient origins and production dates at farm level; methods, metrics, and conditions at processing; and acceptance plus label processing functions at retail. This indicates an event-log view of traceability, where the digital record is updated as the product advances through custody and transformation (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

(3) Integrity protections for the product history. The same use case text describes a “secure identity” protected against tampering and linked to a single shared history that “cannot be rewritten.” That language aligns with immutable logging approaches commonly associated with distributed ledger technology (DLT) or append-only architectures, though the use case itself focuses on the outcome rather than the implementation details (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

(4) Platform interoperability and governance, not just identification. Watson’s public reporting frames the platform as a reference architecture integrating: IoT-based tracing and tracking services, DLT, data analytics, rapid non-invasive authenticity tools, and an AI-supported early warning system for authorities (Ejderyan et al., 2025). In other words, the smart tag is the entry point; the platform is the machinery behind the entry point.

(5) Inclusive access via visual label processing. A notable detail in the use case is support for visually impaired consumers, described via visual label processing and color scanning. This pushes the smart tag platform beyond compliance and into accessibility engineering: the platform is expected to help translate product information into usable form, not merely store it (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

Based on the Watson descriptions, implementing a printed smart tag platform at meaningful scale requires:

Identifier strategy (batch vs. item). The cereal and dairy use case explicitly allows both batch-level and item-level identities, which affects cost, data volume, and recall precision (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

Data governance and accountability. The whitefish abstract emphasizes the importance of coordination, shared standards, and data governance for traceability systems, alongside technical performance (Jakobsen & Ræder, 2025). This is a direct warning: without governance, “smart tags” become “expensive stickers.”

Interoperability-first design. The GS1/EPCIS reference shows a path to interoperable event histories. Without such alignment, each actor’s data remains locally meaningful but globally unusable (Jakobsen & Ræder, 2025).

Closing the loop: verification and response. Watson repeatedly connects traceability to action: targeted consumer contact in dairy, early warning for authorities, and analytical authenticity checks in meat and olive oil (Watson Project, n.d.-a; Ejderyan et al., 2025; Braunersreuther et al., 2025).

PUFs supporting smart tags

Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs) are a type of security mechanism that leverages the inherent physical variabilities of an object to provide a unique, object-specific fingerprint. These variabilities arise from minute, unpredictable differences in macro or micro level due among the other the manufacturing process and properties of materials that are nearly impossible to replicate exactly, even by the original manufacturer. These variations are tiny and random differences much like a fingerprint is unique to each person that cannot be duplicated, even by the manufacturer and the PUF based digital identifier can be used as fingerprint to authenticate objects.

A PUF can be based on many different physical variables, such as the micro-texture of paper, the micro-texture of label paint, or three-dimensional artificial features like dots, holes, and scratches. By using sophisticated feature-detection methods, digital information can be generated that is unique to these physical properties. This information can be used like a fingerprint to identify objects.

In the Watson project, a PUF has been developed based on label painting and three-dimensional artificial features. Compared to other identification methods, the main advantage of this PUF approach is that it is low-cost and can easily leverage existing systems by using standard cameras.

Figure 3 presents a schematic overview of the PUF identification process. The upper part of the figure illustrates the manufacturer-side procedure, where a camera captures an image of a specific area of the object. The image is then digitally processed to generate a unique digital identity, referred to as a “fingerprint.” This fingerprint is stored in a verified data registry, such as a blockchain, for later use. The lower part of the figure shows the customer-side process. The customer takes a picture of the same specific area of the object using a mobile phone camera. A fingerprint is generated from this image using the same method as on the manufacturer's side. The fingerprint generated on the mobile device is then compared with the fingerprint stored in the verified registry. If the fingerprints match, the object is confirmed to be genuine; otherwise, it is identified as a counterfeit.

Figure 3. Semantic picture of a PUF – Fingerprint identification.

Piloting of smart tags in Watson

Using the Finnish cereal and dairy chains as an illustrative case (beer and cheese) (Figure 4), Watson frames smart tags as an enabling layer for digital product identities and “passport-like” records that support rapid verification, accountability, and targeted response when integrity or safety is challenged. This text synthesizes what can be reliably extracted from the Watson cereal and dairy use case description and the project’s publication portfolio, emphasizing platform logic, data and governance requirements, and the role of complementary analytical and AI-based toolsets.

Figure 4. Products used for Finnish cereal and dairy pilot with attached smart tags.

Beer: cereal chain transparency

Scanning the tag enables immediate visibility into where beer was produced, what cereals and raw materials were used, and key processing steps and timelines. The platform value here is “consolidation” (bringing scattered supply-chain evidence into one view) and “accessibility” (making the record usable by non-experts) (Watson Project, n.d.-a).

Cheese and dairy: batch to item-level identity

Each cheese batch, or even each item, can receive a smart identity. Tracking spans milk intake, processing, and store shelf, while consumers verify claims with a single scan. Importantly, the use case explicitly highlights targeted response capability: if something goes wrong (need for product recall), producers can contact affected customers directly (Watson Project, n.d.-a). This is a direct traceability-to-action bridge: identity is not “for reporting,” it is “for intervention.”

Conclusions

Smart tag-based platforms that are built on use of 2D barcodes are feasible for improving traceability within food product value chains. The associated traceability data can be accessed easily, and different stakeholders can have access to data at different levels. 2D barcodes serve as physical identifiers, thus enabling even item-level traceability and updating data in the database. Table 1 presents a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis for Smart Tags.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of Smart Tags.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individualised and dynamic tags for DPPs • Standards compatibility • Machine reading • Cost efficient • Doesn't require special devices • PUFs can be used with 2D barcodes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual reading requires visibility of tag • Physical damage destroys tag • In many cases PUFs provide identity for package, but not for the item itself
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory landscape supports smart tag introduction, e.g. EU ESPR & DPP • Applications outside food and packaging sectors, e.g. textiles and batteries • Minimal barriers for market entry due to a fragmented market with lots of small players 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security and privacy concerns • Competition in a fragmented market • Competition with cheap electronics markers with sensors

Watson project concludes the following recommendations for future development of Smart Tag based traceability platforms:

- Finetuning of the indicator chemistries and development of other technologies, such as protective layers, to be able to control the reaction speed and sensitivity of the indicator to even arrive at semi-quantitative monitoring
- Integration of multiple sensors into a single tag can widen the application cases to food quality monitoring and food safety in a more generic level
- Ensure direct and/or indirect food contact compatibility of the developed indicator chemistries
- Tracking of individual items is already possible in most products, implementing unique identifier on each item should be implemented quite rapidly. This enables track and trace, direct consumer communication, next level food safety and many other applications
- Consumers see it valuable that food items can tell them more than just nutrition values like item history, information about producer and production as well as traceability information
- Smart tags increase consumer trust on the food chain and product quality.

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About

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd is a state owned and controlled non-profit limited liability company established by law and operating under the ownership steering of the Finnish Ministry of Employment and the Economy. VTT is a Research and Technology Organisation (RTO) whose activities are focused on three areas: Carbon neutral solutions, Sustainable products and materials, and Digital technologies. VTT is impact-driven and takes advantage from its wide multi-technological knowledge base to strengthen Finnish and European industrial competitiveness. VTT can combine different technologies, produce information, upgrade technology knowledge, and create business intelligence and value added for its stakeholders. For examples Smart Tag research combines VTT competences from food safety (Process Microbiology and Food safety team) and printed technologies (Flexible sensors and devices team). (www.vttresearch.com)

UpCode is a part of UPC Center situated in Vaasa, Finland. UPC Center is the uniting structure for Wasa Innovation Center, UPC Print, UPC Media and UpCode that is run by UPC Consulting. UPC Consulting is a company with more than a hundred employees and a platina award for being among the strongest companies in Finland. UPC Consulting provides analysis, methods, and concepts. UpCode has been developing smart tags since 2016 TagItSmart project, and is currently focusing on track&trace, authenticity control, lifecycle management and sensing environmental values through smart tags. (www.upcodeworld.com)

HAMI (Häme Vocational Institute LTD) is the subsidiary of Häme University of applied sciences (HAMK). We operate on common campuses with HAMK. HAMI is a multidisciplinary upper secondary vocational school that employs 65 staff members and trains professionals in fields such as dairy production, forestry, and horticulture across its various campus. The institute has around 650 students. At the Sairio campus, the dairy produces a wide range of dairy products, including cheese, ice cream, butter and yogurts, and operates as a production environment that follows industrial processes. The raw milk used in production is sourced from local dairy farms, delivered to a nearby dairy plant, and then transported to HAMI's dairy for further processing. The finished dairy products are sold in the shop of the winery located on the Lepaa campus. (www.hami.fi)

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